

SOME ISSUES OF ENSURING THE INDEPENDENCE OF ADMINISTRATIVE COURT JUDGES

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Abstract: This scientific work highlighted some issues related to the reforms of administrative justice and their implementation in relation to ensuring the independence of judges of administrative courts.

Keywords: justice, administrative court, judiciary, independence of judges, judicial independence, for administrative court judges.

Ensuring the true independence of the judiciary, reliable protection of citizens' rights and freedoms, as well as increasing the level of access to justice are defined as the main priorities of the state policy in the field of further reform of the judicial system in our country.

It should be noted that the procedure for selecting, appointing and electing candidates for the post of judge is one of the important processes in ensuring judicial independence.

According to local and foreign scholars, the procedure for appointing and electing judges is an institution that directly affects judicial independence.

According to the Law "On Courts" the corps of judges in our country is formed on the basis of both appointment and election. However, its procedures and methods differ from each other [1].

According to the contents of Articles 69-70 of this Law, there are three different ways of appointment to the post of judge, and such appointment is made by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Jokorgi Kenes of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, and the Supreme Council of Judges.

Election to the position of judge is carried out in two different ways, according to which judges are elected by the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan and is elected by the Jokorgi Kenes of the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

It is known that in our country, a single procedure for appointing and electing candidates for the position of judges for courts of general jurisdiction and administrative courts has been established.

In our opinion, based on the tasks assigned to the administrative courts, it is necessary to improve the procedure of selection, appointment and election of candidates for administrative court judges based on today's requirements, as well as elimination of existing deficiencies in this regard is extremely important for ensuring the independence of the administrative court.

In order to ensure the full independence of the administrative court, it is necessary to eliminate two important factors. First, it is necessary to eliminate the possible external influence on the administrative court from other authorities, and secondly, the internal influence that can be exerted by the court leadership on the judges of the administrative court.

In this regard, we conducted a survey among the members of the “Judges' Club” and asked “How many of the cases handled by the Administrative Courts involve the intervention of the chairman of the relevant court and his deputy?”. The results of this survey showed a clear proof of our above opinion.

According to the results of the survey, more than **62 percent** of the participants stated that there is no intervention by the chairman and deputy of the court in court cases, while more than **30 percent** of the respondents stated that the intervention of these persons is present in **some cases**, about **3 percent** said that there is intervention in half of the cases, and about **5 percent** said that there is intervention in all cases.

Administrative courts have the authority to hear complaints about the decisions of state bodies or other agencies authorized to carry out administrative-legal activities and the actions (inaction) of their officials, and sometimes to recover

damages caused by officials, to impose fines on them, and in such courts the full independence of the judge, in particular ensuring independence from the leadership of the court is a very important issue.

There is a high probability that the officials of state bodies or other agencies authorized to carry out administrative-legal activities, in particular, hokims of regions, districts, and cities may influence the judge of the administrative court, who is considering a complaint against them, through the leadership of the court (chairmen of the regional administrative court, inter-district administrative court).

Because, in the process of appointing a judge to the post of chairman of the administrative court, there is a certain level of indirect influence of the officials of the state bodies or other agencies authorized to carry out administrative-legal activities, in particular, the hokims of regions, districts, and cities.

According to the fourth part of Article 24¹ of the Law “On the Supreme Council of Judges of the Republic of Uzbekistan”, the Council should study the public opinion on candidates for the post of chairman of regional and Tashkent administrative courts, inter-district administrative courts according to the procedure approved by the Council[2].

The procedure for studying the public opinion about candidates for the position of judge was approved by the decision of the Supreme Council of Judges No. 907 dated November 23, 2018, and in paragraph 13 of this procedure, the public opinion about the candidate who is being considered for appointment to the position of chief judge is to be studied before the issue of the candidate is included in the discussion of the Supreme Council of Judges. And in paragraph 25 of this procedure, it is indicated that opinions expressed by the public will be studied and evaluated by the Supreme Council of Judges.

According to paragraph 11 of this procedure, regional, district, city hokims, heads of internal affairs, tax, customs, justice, public education and other state bodies may be invited to the public opinion survey event.

Therefore, in the process of appointing a judge to the post of chairman or deputy chairman of the administrative court, the officials of state bodies or other agencies authorized to carry out administrative-legal activities, in particular, hokims of regions, districts, and cities may have an indirect influence.

In order to eliminate the participation of the officials of state bodies or other agencies authorized to carry out administrative-legal activities, in particular, the hokims of regions, districts, cities, in the process of appointing a judge to the position of chairman of the administrative court, and to ensure the independence of administrative court judges from the court leadership in the process of carrying out activities on justice it is proposed to introduce the procedure of electing the chairman and deputy chairman of the administrative courts by the judges of this court.

In this case, the candidate for the position of chairman or deputy chairman of the inter-district administrative court should, as a rule, be selected from among the judges of this court, the opinion of the judges should be taken into account when choosing the candidate, and his term of office should be limited to a short period of time (two or three years).

The establishment of such a procedure for the election of the chairman and deputy chairman of the inter-district administrative court, firstly, serves to ensure the independence of the court leadership from other bodies of state power, and secondly, it sharply reduces the possibility of the court chairman and deputy chairman influencing the activities of the administrative court judge related to the implementation of judicial activities. Taking into account that his term of office is not long and that he is elected by the judges of this court, any intervention of the chairman of the court and the deputy chairman in the activities of the judges creates the possibility that he will not be elected for the next terms of leadership.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the same requirements are set for all court judges, and the requirements based on the specialization of the courts are not provided for when appointing a person to the position of a judge.

According to the general rule established in Articles 67 and 68 of the Law “On Courts”, a citizen of the Republic of Uzbekistan who has reached the age of thirty-five, has a higher legal education and at least seven years of work experience in a legal specialty can be a judge of an inter-district, district, city court, or a regional military court.

Today's intensive reforms, including reforms in the field of public administration, require not only thorough training, but also specific qualifications, skills in working with legislation in the field of administration from judges who have the authority to consider cases on disputes arising from administrative and other public-legal relations.

In other words, the judge of the administrative court should fully understand the work of the person who has authority in the course of his activities. Because the judge of the administrative court in the process of considering the administrative case is required to give the task to the person who has the power of authority not in a general way (presentation of evidence, implementation of action, etc.), but in a specific form (submitting specific information from a specific information system of a state body or sending a questionnaire with a specific content to a specific office and taking appropriate action based on specific documents, etc.).

For this, the judge of the administrative court is required to have certain qualifications and skills in the field of public administration.

In our opinion, based on the tasks assigned to the administrative courts and the specific features of the activity of the administrative courts, it is suggested to set one more requirement for the candidates for the post of judge, in addition to the requirements listed above, when appointing a person to the position of a judge of the administrative court, i.e. the requirement that a person should have at least two years of experience as a management employee in state authority and management bodies.

According to Y.N. Starilov's rightly expressed opinion, the judge who considers the dispute between the citizen and the public authority should know

in detail the right of management, the relevant management practice and administrative legislation[3].

The need for the presence of such skills in administrative court judges was also emphasized by the legal scientist G. Khakimov, according to his opinion, officials who consider administrative-legal disputes, i.e. judges, should have sufficient knowledge and skills in the field of public administration[4].

Establishing in the Law “On Courts” the requirement that a candidate for the post of administrative court judge must have a certain length of service as a management employee in state authority and management bodies, firstly, serves to effectively ensure the rights and legal interests of citizens and legal entities in relations with administrative bodies, and secondly, creates a basis for resolving such disputes in a qualitative and speedy manner.

List of references:

1. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Courts”. <https://www.lex.uz/docs/5534923>.
2. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the Supreme Council of Judges of the Republic of Uzbekistan”. <https://www.lex.uz/docs/3153668>.
3. Starilov Yu.N. Administrative justice: problems of theory. Voronezh, 1998. P.106.
4. G.T. Khakimov. Problems of development of administrative justice in Uzbekistan. Monograph. // T.: TDYuI Publishing House, 2009. Pages 13-14.